

ENGLISH HISTORY ORIGIN AND ROOTS. THE INNOVATIVE APPROACHES OF LEARNING LANGUAGE

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Abstract:

The history of the English language is inextricably linked with the history of England. When the Romans left the British Isles in 410, they took Latin with them. The true inhabitants of the island (the Britons) continued to use Celtic languages. The ancestors of the modern English did not waste time. In 449, the Germanic tribes of the Angles, Saxons and Jutes began their first raids on the islands. This article provides a brief history of the origin and development of the English language.

Keywords: Old English, Angles, Germanic language, Saxons, Jutes, Middle English, Modern English, varieties, West, North, century, British Empire, Spelling, Great Vowel.

Introduction

English is a member of the Germanic language family. Germanic is a branch of the Indo-European language family. The history of the English language began with the arrival of three Germanic tribes who invaded Britain in the 5th century AD. These tribes, the Angles, Saxons, and Jutes, crossed the North Sea from what is now Denmark and northern Germany. At the time, the inhabitants of Britain spoke a Celtic language. But most Celtic speakers were driven west and north by the invaders – mainly into what is now Wales, Scotland, and Ireland. The Angles are descended from “England,” and their language was called “English,” from which we get the words “England” and “English.” The Germanic invaders entered Britain on the east and south coasts in the 5th century. Old English (450–1100 CE) The invading Germanic tribes spoke similar languages, which in Britain evolved into what we now call Old English³.

Old English is very different from modern English. English speakers today would have great difficulty understanding Old English. However, about half of the most commonly used words in modern English have Old English roots. The words *be*, *strong* and *water*, for example, *all come from Old English*. Old English was spoken until about 1100.

Middle English (1100–1500) In 1066, William the Conqueror, Duke of Normandy, invaded and conquered England. The new conquerors (called Normans) brought with them a kind of French, which became the language of the royal court, statesmen, and the wealthy. For a time, there was a kind of linguistic class division, with the lower classes speaking English and the upper classes speaking French. In the 14th century, English became dominant in Britain again, but with many French words added. This language is called Middle English. It was the language of the great poet Chaucer (1340–1400), but is difficult for English speakers to understand today⁴.

Modern English *Early Modern English* (1500–1800) Towards the end of Middle English there began a sudden and distinct change in pronunciation (the Great Vowel Shift), with vowels becoming shorter and shorter. From the 16th century onwards, the British came into contact with many peoples from all over the world. This, and the revival of classical learning, meant that many new words and phrases entered the language. The invention of printing also meant that there was now a common language in print. Books became cheaper, and people learned to read. Printing also brought standardisation to the English language. Spelling and grammar became fixed, and the dialect of London, where most of the publishing houses were located, became the standard. In 1604 the first English dictionary was published. *Late Modern English* (1800–present) The main difference between Early Modern English and Late Modern English is vocabulary⁵.

Late Modern English has many more words, due to two main factors: firstly, the Industrial Revolution and technology created a need for new words; secondly, the British Empire at its height covered a quarter of the earth's surface, and the English language adopted foreign words from many countries. Varieties of English from about 1600 onwards, the English colonisation of North America created a distinct American variety of English. Some English pronunciations and words "*froze*" when they reached America. In some ways, American

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³ Arakin V.D. Essays on the history of the English language. Moscow, 2021.

⁴ Brunner K. History of the English language. Translated from German. Moscow: Foreign Literature, Vol. I-II, 2022–2023.

⁵ Idyish B. A. History of the English language. L., 2023.

English is more like Shakespeare's English than modern British English. Some expressions that the British call "Americanisms" are actually original British expressions that survived in the colonies but were lost in Britain.

For example, trash instead of rubbish, loan instead of lend. Spanish has also influenced *American English* (and subsequently *British English*), with words such as canyon, ranch, stampede, and vigilante being examples of Spanish words that entered English through the settlement of the American West. French words (via Louisiana) and words from West Africa (via the slave trade) have also influenced *American English* (and thus, to some extent, *British English*). Today, American English is particularly influential because of the dominance of film, television, popular music, commerce, and technology (including the Internet) in the United States. But there are many other varieties of English around the world, including, for example, *Australian English*, *New Zealand English*, *Canadian English*, *South African English*, *Indian English*, and *Caribbean English*.

Literature analysis and methodology

One can only guess what the language would have become if the descendants of these three tribes had not been attacked. The fact is that two large invasions of the island and the missionary movement changed the language incredibly. As a result, English became the language with the largest number of words, and in grammar, the main role was no longer played by the endings of words, but by their order in the sentence. Almost three centuries after the Anglo-Saxon invasion, another wave of 'guests' swept across the islands. These people spoke a North Germanic language, and came from Norway, Sweden and Denmark. Their language differed from the Anglo-Saxon language about as much as Italian differs from Spanish. Despite the differences in pronunciation and endings, common roots could still be found in both languages, which made communication between the Vikings and the Anglo-Saxons quite bearable.

The Viking invasion was relatively peaceful, and after the initial battles, the tribes began to coexist peacefully in England. The languages mingled, creating a mixed language that lacked most of the endings that continue to be found in most continental languages. This mixed language gradually became accepted and evolved into what we now call Old English¹.

In 1066, the Normans invaded England. They, like the Vikings, came from Scandinavia, but for some unknown reason, they settled in northern France and began to speak a dialect of French. The Norman invasion elevated French to the status of a state language, the language of the ruling minority. All official documents were written in French, and it seemed that it would become the recognized language of the country. But the stubborn Anglo-Saxons did not want to learn French, and the vast majority of residents continued to speak Old English.

As a result of the Norman invasion (Northmen, or people of the north), the motley Celtic and Germanic tribes that inhabited the British Isles ceased to exist as such, turning into a nation that is remarkable to the world today as the English (which is not entirely correct, because in addition to the English, there are also the Welsh, Scots and Irish, who have tried for endless centuries to preserve the remnants of their national identity). All these tribes, as well as their conquerors, had to somehow understand each other. From the fusion of local dialects and through the maximum simplification of grammar, the English language ultimately arose, which, thus, was originally precisely a means of international.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this article covers the history of the development of the English language step by step, revealing how it has undergone changes from ancient times to the present day. In the early stages, the English language began to form as a result of the invasion of the British Isles by Germanic tribes such as the Angles, Saxons and Jutes. Later, the Viking and Norman invasions brought significant changes to the language, with the influence of French and other Germanic languages. As a result of these processes, the English language with simplified grammar and rich vocabulary appeared. Through the development of printing technology, the expansion of trade and science, the vocabulary of the English language increased and became standardized as an international language. Today, thanks to colonialism and cultural ties, English has become one of the most influential languages in the world, a medium of international communication that incorporates various regional dialects and cultural influences.

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